

Navigating the Evolution of Language and Brain: A Journey through Time and Technology

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February, 2024

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10620155>

Introduction

Embarking on a historical voyage through the intricate landscape of language and the brain, this essay unfolds the chronology of discoveries and technologies that have shaped our understanding. From the classic models of Broca and Wernicke and the cutting-edge neuroimaging tools to the Dual Stream model and computational modeling, the narrative seeks to weave a coherent tapestry of the journey into the neural bases of language. Let us begin with the definitions of language and how it is processed in our brain.

What is Language?

There exist numerous definitions of language, yet only some particularly pertain to its manifestation within the brain. In 1957, Noam Chomsky characterized language as a cognitive tool. However, with advancements in neuroimaging technology, it was discovered that language and cognition are not the same. Fedorenko and Varley (2006) found out that language areas in the brain are highly engaged during language tasks but not during nonlinguistic activities. The study provides evidence for the independence of language from these cognitive abilities, namely arithmetic processing, executive functions, theory of mind, music processing, and spatial navigation.

Another pertinent definition within the neurological context draws inspiration from Saussure's structuralism, articulated in 1916. Saussure's framework provides a foundational understanding of language representation at distinct levels, ranging from elemental components, such as sounds and words to the higher-order organization of sentences and meaning. Saussure's insights align with the concept of how linguistic structures are encoded and processed in the brain.

How does the brain work?

Our brain, much like other organs, is composed of cells. Specifically, the cells facilitating communication within the brain or with other organs are known as nerve cells. These cells are densely packed in the brain and extend throughout the body, resembling a tree. Dendrites branch in multiple directions from the cell body, receiving incoming signals, while axons, like slender extensions, transmit signals (Figure 1.) The messages are conveyed in the form of electric currents, enabling us to recognize when the brain processes language. As this neural activity occurs, the body fulfills an energy requirement through blood supply. Both electrical signals and blood flow in the brain allow us to observe brain activity with neuroimaging tools.

Figure 1: Nerve cell structure (Rai et al 2013)

Language in the Brain

Before advanced neuroimaging tools, pioneering neuroscientists relied on brain-damaged patients, as well as an invasive method known as Deficit-Lesion Method, to infer the connection between specific brain regions and language functions. This method aims to investigate the cognitive deficits or impairments that arise as a result of brain lesions or damage in particular areas. Consequently, Broca (1861) and Wernicke (1874) revealed language localization: Broca's area, located in the frontal lobe of the left hemisphere and linked to language production, and Wernicke's area, found in the posterior part of the left superior temporal gyrus and associated with comprehension (Figure 2.)

Figure 2: Broca and Wernicke Areas (The British Psychological Society 2016)

Neuroimaging Tools

In the early 20th century, neuroscientists were able to visualize the structure and function of the brain non-invasively using neuroimaging tools. It was found during this time that the language region in the brain is left-dominant. These tools, both electromagnetic and blood based, contribute to the study of language in the brain offering unique advantages in terms of spatial or temporal resolution.

Electromagnetic-based techniques, such as Electroencephalography or EEG (1924,) Magnetoencephalography or MEG (1972,) and Computed Tomography or CT (1973,) rely on electrical or magnetic fields to capture rapid changes of neural activities in the brain. Therefore, they provide excellent temporal resolution with millisecond precision (in case of EEG and MEG,) yet poor spatial resolution as they struggle to precisely identify the regions where neural activity occurs. Although MEG gives a better spatial resolution than EEG thanks to its dependence on the magnetic fields

compared to electrical potentials of EEG which are often interfered by the scalp and tissues, MEG is more expensive due to complex equipment and setting requirements (Figure 4.) EEG, on the other hand, is simpler, cheaper, and widely available. EEG also provides excellent temporal resolution (Figure 3.)

Figure 3 (Left): A person undergoing an EEG Test in the 1950s (Charismatic Planet 2020)
 Figure 4 (Right): MEG experimental setup (Corsi 2023)

Hemodynamic-based measurements like Positron Emission Tomography or PET (1963,) Magnetic Resonance Imaging or MRI (1977 Figure 5,) and Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging or fMRI (1990) rely on changes in blood flow to infer neural activity. These techniques provide high spatial resolution, enabling precise localization of brain activity to specific regions, yet low temporal resolution as blood flow does not happen instantly. The difference between MRI and fMRI is that MRI measures the structure or anatomy of the brain while fMRI measures the functions of the brain.

Figure 5: Components of an MRI scanner (Massaro 2015)

The differences between electromagnetic and blood based methods were highlighted in Vartiainen et al's study (2011) as the team compared neural activation patterns in a silent single-word reading task using MEG/EEG and fMRI. While the scan results of these methods involve largely comparable brain regions, the specific patterns of activation and their interpretation differ between them (Figure 6.) This study, therefore, emphasizes the complementary nature of hemodynamic and electrophysiological

measures taking into account different generation mechanisms when interpreting neural activity patterns in the brain.

Figure 6: MEG and fMRI activations and stimulus effects in the occipital cortex (Vartiainen et al 2011)

The introduction of MRI and fMRI techniques in the late 20th century unveils the power of high-resolution imaging enabling researchers to navigate the brain's terrain and witness the neural ballet accompanying language processing. This has brought about numerous cutting-edge research resulting in advancements and discoveries of language and the brain. One of those contemporary findings is the Dual Stream Model of Language Processing (Hickok & Poeppel 2004; Saura et al 2008), inspired by the Dual Stream Model of Visual Processing (Goodale & Milner 1992). In Hickok and Poeppel's study (2004,) it was found that the dorsal stream involves sound-to-motor mapping and is responsible for speech production while the ventral stream maps sound to meaning and is crucial for speech comprehension (Figure 7.) In addition, the findings from several studies (Saura et al 2008;

Binder et al 2000 in Figure 8; Poeppel & Assaneo 2020) also strongly align with the functional organization of the Dual Stream Model. The Dual Stream Model signifies that language processes in the brain take place in multiple regions as a network rather than specific spots.

Figure 7 (Left): The dual-stream model of the functional anatomy of language (Hickok & Poeppel 2007)
 Figure 8 (Right): Dual pathway network for language (Saura et al 2008)

Looking back through time, the understanding of language processing in the brain has evolved through distinct stages. In the 19th century, pioneers like Broca and Wernicke made foundational observations, linking specific brain regions to language functions through lesion studies. The mid-20th century witnessed the recognition of left hemisphere dominance and the use of brain stimulation to map precise language areas. Advancements in neuroimaging from the late 20th century to the present provided detailed insights into brain activity during language tasks, revealing regional specialization and the exploration of language networks. In the contemporary era, researchers recognize that language processing involves a distributed network of brain regions rather than specific language centers.

Computational Neuroscience of Language Processing

As the understanding of how the brain processes language is deepening and advancing, new techniques and methodologies in computer science emerged. These innovations, especially machine learning algorithms, as well as simulation and modeling tools, allow scientists to develop computational models that have a wide range of capabilities. These computational models are divided into two types: models of representation and models of processing (Vliet 2022.)

Marijn van Vliet (2022) continued to explain that models of representation like Connectionist Model and Semantic Embedding Model are a network of related concepts of abstract semantics that aims to organize data in such a way that it is organized in the brain. Many studies (Rumelhart & Todd 1993, Mikolov et al 2013, Deyne et al 2018 in Figure 10, and Kivisaari et al 2019 in Figure 9) employed such models to understand language perception and generate a semantic embedding network. The semantic network is a lexicographic network where words are identified by their locations in semantic space. Alexander Huth and his team (2016) revealed semantic maps that tile the human cerebral cortex by mapping the semantic representations of words (Word2Vec embedding space) onto neural activity patterns (fMRI brain activity embedding space) (Figure 11.)

Figure 9: Semantic network of the word “dog” from “Small World of Words” project (Deyne et al 2018)

Figure 10: Representation of the word “potato” in a 2D semantic space, as well as a corresponding fMRI brain map (Kivisaari et al 2019)

Figure 11: The map of semantic selectivity across the cortex using voxel-wise modeling of fMRI data (Huth et al 2016)

Marijn (2022) mentioned another kind of model — models of processing. These models aim to replicate how the brain transforms linguistic data from one representation into another. They usually come into a form of artificial neural network, such as perceptron network and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), where each layer in the model is a representation of stimulus, and the computation to transition from one representation to the next is symbolized by connections between the layers. Marijn and team (2022) used CNN (Figure 12) to build a model that can predict brain activity of a word given its representation in Word2Vec space (Figure 13.)

Figure 12: Overview of the proposed computational model of visual word recognition in the brain (Van Vliet et al 2022)

Figure 13: Relationship between the computational model and MEG responses (Vliet et al 2022)

The Symphony of Man and Machine

Along the timeline, the jigsaw puzzle of language processes in the brain has been put together piece by piece with the help of technological and scientific advancements. The mysteries of how the brain processes language have been unveiled to a certain extent. This branch of knowledge has intertwined with other disciplines and expanded continuously from solely understanding the mechanisms of the brain in processing language to exploring and utilizing such knowledge for various applications. Recent studies incorporate knowledge of neuroscience of language processing in the development of Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs), assistive technologies, and cognitive enhancers. This envisaged era promises a seamless integration of these innovations to enhance human linguistic capabilities and foster a symbiotic relationship between technology and the neural symphony that underlies language.

Conclusion

Our journey through time and technology unveils a narrative of continuous discovery and creation in the realm of language and the brain. From the foundational models of Broca and Wernicke and the sophisticated tools of contemporary neuroimaging to the Dual Stream Model of Language Processing and computational modeling, each milestone contributes to the intricate tapestry of our understanding.

As we gaze into the future, the envisioned synergy between human brain studies and cutting-edge technology hints at a new chapter in the symphony of language, where the boundaries of neurolinguistics exploration continue to expand.

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